

SYSTEM LEVEL - FINDINGS MATRIX

Market Practices	Composite Activities	Designable Elements	Underlying Single Activities	Consequences	Illustrative Quotes from In-depth Interviews (Sayings)	Excerpts from Unobtrusive Observation and Document Analysis (Doings)
			Facing a lack of trust	Unravels a distinguished representation of the market to be overcome	<p>"In the beginning I used to spend shoe soles to be heard, like this, in many places that do not even want to hear us: 'oh no pyramid, I do not even want to hear.'" (P13)</p> <p>"[...] people have always associated with deep web, with those guys from Silk. And when in reality, they were unmasked exactly because they used bitcoin [...]'" (P5)</p> <p>"And most of the time there is discrimination, many times we are not considered big companies, serious companies there are companies that turn around and get involved in problems of fraud, pyramids and that ends up tarnishing the name." (P8)</p>	<p>Firm F has provided on their website a section to answer Frequently Asked Questions. Among the questions that they answer, some are focused on why they use blockchain, the tokens' role in their ecosystem, where the firm is localized, the history behind the business, etc. They also provide a page to clarify who is the founders and the team behind Firm F. This information could help strengthen the company's credibility (content extracted from Firm F's website).</p>
			Working to legitimize and demystify	Diffuses social movements to legitimize business and change the market perceptions	<p>"Education is fundamental. People still do not understand this, this market, they still think it is a pyramid thing, a money launderer, lack of knowledge... The Brazilian market is still far behind in that." (P13)</p> <p>"The basic pillar of our entire marketing is to demystify and educate." (P8)</p> <p>"So our idea is to demystify. Our idea is this, to really make it easy, to show that cryptocurrency is something simple. Unfortunately, there is much discrimination in relation to crypto. Our idea is to bring this simplicity [...]'" (P12)</p>	<p>Firm D has been posting in their Instagram profile a series of short videos in which they briefly explain questions from their followers about the cryptosets. In this way, they may capture the attention of the customer and clarify the advantages of investing in crypto (content extracted from Firm D Instagram profile).</p>
	Educating the market (SUWITO et al., 2017)	Capabilities Language Information Symbols Social Norms	Educating the market to spread the potential	Allows to convince the stakeholders about the benefits	<p>"I understand that I also have this responsibility to create a market. So I need to look at the person who does not know bitcoin, I need to teach him why it makes sense to expose himself to it." (P7)</p> <p>"So we are also trying to educate for the people do not expose themselves more than they would tolerate in this market." (P13)</p> <p>"So, we have been tackling a lot from this angle, using the investment agents' evangelization channel, and showing them that literally everyone needs to have a little cryptoset in their portfolio." (P14)</p> <p>"So, of course, every two months I promote a course focused on the cryptocurrency. So I ended up taking this course so much that I wrote my ebook to save my speech." (P9)</p> <p>"We had technical articles for specialized websites. [...] It's always cool. I think you have to 'spread the word', do this, not only as a project, but as a government.'" (P3)</p> <p>"We also try to maintain a good relationship with the influencers, so participate in a podcast, in third-party lives, [...] we have a good contact with them, there to open opportunities. I think that, yes, digital media." (P13)</p>	<p>Firm C has been exploring a franchise model in Brazil with dozens of partners that have to be appropriately aligned and coordinated towards approaching their clients. In an Instagram post, they highlight that their franchised agents are immersed in training camps to become qualified for personal and financial growth (content extracted from Firm C's Instagram profile).</p>
			Looking different ways for educating the market	Boosts the capability of attracting different stakeholders		<p>Firm D has been delivering a series of crypto-based content in its YouTube channel in which they address regulatory and technical issues. This content is also diverse in terms of format, varying from in-depth interviews to short videos introducing concepts (content extracted from Firm D's YouTube channel).</p>

Representational Practices

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Co-developing an innovative ecosystem (CHESBROUGH; SCHWARTZ, 2007)	Capabilities Actors Rules and Know-how	Gaining credibility through strategic players	Helps to build an image that represents a reliable business	<p>"Her (CEO of Firm F) relationship with the [omitted], the access we have to the [omitted] is very important, one of the greatest assets that we have today for us to achieve big agendas." (P17)</p> <p>"With regard to the [omitted], I think that was almost kind of a game changer at the time for us, because it was essential to have a credit card brand for the business and a known one, right?" (P7)</p> <p>"In addition, having people who bring a brand like [omitted] makes a huge difference because they are products that work on a large scale and in consumer confidence." (P14)</p>	<p>The multinational digital payment company that support the credit card of Firm B has announced in their website the established partnership, thus highlighting the pioneer connection of Cryptoeconomics with traditional financial system in Brazil (content extracted from the website of the digital payment partner).</p>				
						Nurturing networking and know-how	Increases the knowledge and competence	<p>"[...] we did two blockchain government events, and the initial idea was to map what blockchain initiatives were in the public sector." (P6)</p> <p>"For me, the highest point of our career is having been invited to a round table at [omitted], an event in Singapore [...] and hearing from them that they will be coming with everything through the stablecoins." (P11)</p> <p>"So how do we acquire knowledge. One thing is you read on Medium how a project is; another thing you go there and use it. So these projects, for example, DeFi, I have done almost everything, I have already lost money, I have had a problem, but it is part of my job, obviously, we do not do it in the fund, we do it outside the fund, so we are two first-rate users. We have used a lot of things." (P16)</p>	<p>We observed the co-lead of Firm A in organizing two major events in the last years approaching the use of blockchain for governments. These events accounts with the presence of different players of the ecosystem (content extracted from website event organized by Firm A).</p>
Cooperating to enlarge the market	Opens up new opportunities for growing together	<p>"So there are players, each with a slightly different angle in terms of the value proposition, but everyone is playing on the same market. I really believe that everyone is there, people may not understand, or not understand over not thinking a little, but everyone is helping each other." (P14)</p> <p>"I think three cases that offer similar products. And the relationship we have is quite good. I think that is a friendly competition. We understand that if you have a single crypto fund, you have nothing, because there is no market. When you have competitors, you have a market." (P16)</p> <p>"So, I do not know if other players see it as the way I see it, if they really want to kill, if they already want to start fighting, fight among the companies themselves. Start killing the competition to keep a small share, or if they want to expand the market as a whole. [...] I think it is not a time to fight for share, it is a time to expand share as a whole." (P8)</p>	<p>Firm B has made an Instagram post in which they communicated the manual of best practices and self-regulation developed by the ABCripto (Brazilian Association of Cryptoeconomics). The ABCripto is composed of the major Brazilian crypto exchanges and is devoted to bringing together players from the cryptoassets and blockchain world for dialogue with the public authorities, as well as to carry out actions in favor of technological development and innovation in the sector (content extracted from Firm B Instagram profile and ABCripto website).</p>						

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Normalizing Practices	Welcoming and shaping well-defined rules to advance the business (CUMMING et al., 2019)	Market Standards Regulations Information	Perceiving a progress towards an agenda pro-regulation	Helps to develop an overall trust on the market	<p>"I... in fact, I see regulation as a good thing in general, if it is done with the purpose of helping or dictating the minimum rules. That is the least you have to do to be free there. That I see as good because it differentiates the chaff from the wheat. What I see with bad eyes, and sometimes the line is fine between one thing and another, is to enforce very high barriers that inhibit innovation. I do not know... minimum capital requirement." (P7)</p> <p>"In this point of view, when you look at crypto as investment, we are totally pro-regulation. We really have to have it, otherwise, we are not going to move. If it is not regulated, prohibited, the market will not develop." (P13)</p> <p>"In relation to the government, that has been very calm. Today we have an API integrated with the Federal Revenue and we send to them in the following month all the company's movement, where it gathers the tax at source on the lease contracts. We also demand the issuance of a Service Invoice from our autonomous crypto agents." (P11)</p>	<p>Firm A has posted in its Instagram profile a specific post clarifying how the company is legal in the light of Brazilian law. They clarify the Normative Instruction in which validates their business model (content extracted from Firm B's Instagram).</p>
					<p>"And on the side of the regulatory sector, the legal side, ABCripto created self-regulation to prevent fraud. So, the good practices of companies, what companies should ask from customers, regarding information, so to avoid frauds." (P8)</p> <p>"Since the beginning, we used our approaches to talk to the CVM staff, i.e., people that are directly or indirectly responsible for investment funds. One CVM member came on our YouTube channel to do a YouTube live with us, we really try to try to nurture, nurture these relationships." (P14)</p> <p>"I am super proud to say that I cooperated with her, before she was born, because she was born in September 17 and that's when we were able to launch our retail fund." (P15)</p> <p>"For the case of standards, I think that the overall maturity is still very low, the standards that are coming out are standards of nomenclature or standards of platform comparisons or how the platforms work. They are very explanatory or comparative and less enabling." (P2)</p>	<p>Firm D has conducted a video in which they discussed with a representative of the Movable Values Commission the role of sandboxes for encouraging innovative solutions in the sector and what are the perspectives for the fund market based on cryptoassets (content extracted from YouTube channel to Firm D).</p>
			Figuring out uncertainties and barriers	Identifies particular challenges to be faced	<p>"How do public entities account, how do public entities move, transfer assets such as a token, a cryptoasset like this. You do not have the legislation that supports this, and then you reduce the incentives for this to happen. It remains a very abstract thing, very ethereal, and the people are always very conservative." (P6)</p> <p>"So, the government can be very good, but it can arrive and, man, you are prohibited from operating here. Which creates insecurity. There have already been congressmen, senators, talking about banning business." (P7)</p>	<p>Firm E has the routine of publicizing monthly market reports in their website. By analyzing these reports we could notice the feeling of the portfolio manager as the market evolves, including its perception of changes and opportunities. They very often addresses regulatory issues and movements of worldwide players (content extracted from Firm E website).</p>